

MODERN REQUIREMENTS FOR TEACHING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE FOR LAWYERS

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Annotation: *The article deals with the formation of speech skills and abilities of students in the classroom in the Russian language and culture of speech, the preparation of professional speech for future lawyers, the existing problems in the study of the Russian language, the difficulties in presenting their thoughts in the literary language, students who graduated from school with the Kyrgyz language of instruction. A modern person who receives education in universities should choose high-quality training.*

Key words: *speech, lawyer, words, learning.*

The article draws attention to the goals, objectives, content of the program material on the discipline. The priority is determined by the spiritual and moral orientation of the lesson, its integrity, the internal interconnectedness of the parts of the lesson. The specifics of the organization of the Russian language lesson involves the development of speech and work to prevent errors. The Russian language lesson, organized taking into account the requirements of the implementation of the second generation standards, will help the teacher to intensify the cognitive activity of students, arouse

interest in the subject, form universal learning activities, and increase the level of development.

Legal language is the language of strict formulations, so lawyers must adhere to definitions that are adequate to the text of the law. That enhances the culture of speech. So, they often write: they started a case, but they don't start a case, but they initiate it. They don't postpone the case, but the trial of the case. The speech of a lawyer should be expressive, which means that stamps and patterns should be avoided as much as possible and to a greater extent use capacious words and

constructions from the arsenal of the language.

And of course, the lawyer's speech must be clean. So, using foreign words, the speaker must be sure that he will be understood correctly. In the last decade, borrowed words have increasingly appeared in professional speech, which is not always justified: corrective (instead of correction), indifferent (instead of indifferent), limit (instead of limit), manager (instead of manager).

Anyone who has not mastered the norms of pronunciation and word usage cannot reach the heights of rhetorical skill, which is so necessary in the training of lawyers, in particular foreign ones. We believe that the return of the course of rhetoric to universities is necessary, especially to the faculties of law. At a minimum, optional special courses in rhetoric should be introduced into RFL programs. Teaching the art of the word should be carried out with the obligatory consideration of legal practice in the new social conditions.

Teaching the Russian language as a means of forming socio-cultural competence is of particular relevance when teaching students studying international economic relations. Let us turn to the language of business, because without knowing the language

business partner contacts are always defective. There is an opinion that learning

business language is a purely pragmatic task, ultimately aimed at making a profit - the main object of business contacts. This task is solved through

mastering the necessary terminology, typical lexical and syntactic constructions

in their functional significance. The content of training is dosed and purposeful. However, experience shows that the business language is not limited by strict professional boundaries and comes into contact with various aspects, with the old and new in human existence, and, consequently, with elements of universal and national culture. In order to adequately and effectively use the business language for pragmatic purposes, it is necessary to constantly make excursions into cultural linguistics.

The result of multilateral business contacts at the level of states and peoples are numerous language borrowings, universals in language practice,

migrations. These phenomena need comments that facilitate communication

activities in a foreign language market, and enrich the mind of a student of a foreign language

business language. That is why, along with a purely linguistic (lexico-syntactic and terminological) orientation of learning, it is necessary to pay special attention to

on the cultural aspect of business language. It seems that without this knowledge of the business language will remain inferior.

The most important source of studying the language and culture of the country was and remains the text.

Any text is subject to perception and comprehension in the context of the culture that creates it. The text, understood as a cultural phenomenon, plays an important role in the learning process.

Russian language. Perception and understanding of the text form a single process and determine the semantic integration of the text with the student.

The modern lesson of the Russian language and literature in the context of the introduction of a new generation should include the following six main stages:

mobilization (implies the inclusion of students in active intellectual activity)

goal-setting (students independently formulate the objectives of the lesson according to the scheme "remember → learn → learn")

awareness of the insufficiency of existing knowledge (the teacher contributes to the emergence of a problem situation in the lesson, during the analysis of which students understand that the existing knowledge is not enough to solve it)

communication (search for new knowledge in a pair, in a group);

mutual verification, mutual control;

reflection (the student's awareness and reproduction in speech of what he learned new and what he learned in the lesson).

Какие же требования предъявляются к современному уроку русского языка и литературы в условиях введения:

- A well-organized lesson in a well-equipped classroom should have a good start and a good end.

- the teacher must plan his activities and the activities of students, clearly formulate the theme, purpose, objectives of the lesson;

- the lesson should be problematic and developing: the teacher himself aims at cooperation with students and knows how to direct students to cooperate with the teacher and classmates;

- the teacher organizes problem and search situations, activates the activity of students;

- the conclusion is made by the students themselves;

- minimum of reproduction and maximum of creativity and co-creation;

- time saving and health saving;
- the focus of the lesson is on children;

- taking into account the level and capabilities of students, which takes into account such aspects as the profile of the class, the aspirations of students, the mood of children;

- the ability to demonstrate the methodological art of the teacher;

- feedback planning;
- the lesson should be kind.

Now, in accordance with the new standards, it is necessary, first of all, to strengthen the child's motivation to learn the Russian language and literature, to demonstrate to him that schoolwork is not about obtaining knowledge abstracted from life, but on the contrary - the necessary preparation for life, its recognition, search useful information and the skills to apply it in real life. Lessons should be built according to a completely different scheme.

If now the explanatory and illustrative method of work is most common, when the teacher, standing in front of the class, explains the topic, and then conducts a selective survey, then in accordance with the changes, the emphasis should be on the interaction of

students and the teacher, as well as the interaction of the students themselves. The student must become a living participant in the educational process.

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